

Hypothetical Protein

Conserved Oligomeric Golgi Subunit 4

Endoglycoceramidase

Annexin

Base Pairs

Mitochondrial Aspartate tRNA ligase

Supplementary Figure 7-11 - Gene models of genes that form the large subtelomeric segmentally duplicated gene clusters. Supplementary Figure 7 – 11 represent the hypothetical protein, conserved oligomeric golgi subunit 4, endoglycoceramidase, annexin, mitochondrial aspartate tRNA ligase clusters respectively. Arrows indicate exons (only coding sequences, excludes UTRs) for each gene, coloured by exon number except for the case of the hypothetical protein cluster. Seven genes (marked with asterisks) are lacking the canonical (as defined by the 39 “full length” gene models) first and second exons. These models were aligned and coloured relative to the third exon (for example Smp_349650.1).